

Stream Segregation: Utilizing Harmonic Variance in Auditory Graphs

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ABSTRACT

The sonification of line charts, from which auditory line charts are produced is a common sonification strategy used today. This paper examines timbre as a potentially useful sonic dimension for relaying information in sonified line charts. A user-study is presented in which 43 participants were tasked with identifying particular trends among multiple distractor trends using sonified data. These sonified data comprised frequency-mapped trends isolated with the gradual enrichment of harmonic content, using a sawtooth wave as a guideline for the overall harmonic structure. Correlations between harmonic content and identification success rates were examined. Results from the study indicate that the majority of participants consistently chose the sample with the most harmonics when deciding which sonified trend best represented the visual equivalent. However, this confidence decreased with each harmonic addition to the point of complete uncertainty when choosing between a sample with 3 harmonics and a sample with 4 harmonics.

1. INTRODUCTION

Sonification today is a familiar tool used to reinforce or replace a visual representation of data. However, despite significant development and successful application across a variety of different fields [1–3], there remains a certain degree of skepticism in its suitability for relaying precise chunks of information accurately within scientific contexts [4]. Such skepticism is often justified, as many sonification projects are implemented with little theoretical discussion, particularly in how sonified elements are precisely processed by an intricate human auditory system. A significant percentage of robust sonification techniques result in publications that support findings based on results, of which include little theoretical discussion beforehand in relation to the human auditory system. It is commonplace that various sonification projects require specific and often entirely unique techniques be applied [5]. It is the opinion of the authors that justifications for choosing such techniques can often be based on ‘common-sense’, without reference to important aspects of the auditory system, for example stream segregation and temporal resolution.

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In recent years, there have been impressive projects tackling real-time processing and accessibility features within applications [6, 7]. However, there are few publications that reference known phenomena occurring within human auditory perception addressed by Auditory Scene Analysis (ASA). Stream segregation, illusory continuity, fusion and decomposition of complex sounds are just a few of the fundamental principles presented in Bregman’s ASA treatise [8]. Since its inception, this system has been expanded and adopted in various systematic approaches to modeling auditory perception, as well as being applied in other ‘directions’ as Bregman himself explains in “Three directions in research on auditory scene analysis” [9]. Given the compelling evidence that ASA is the basis of how we understand and perceive complex sounds in our environment, it stands to reason that it should play an equally important and fundamental role when designing complex sounds for the purpose of communicating information from machine to human user. This paper aims to show how long-existing research into stream segregation can support even the most basic models of sonification; more specifically how the perceptual ‘grouping’ of tones based on complexity or purity can be used to segregate sonified streams of data [10]. The idea here is that where multiple auditory streams playing concurrently is required or preferable, timbre can be used to focus or isolate a particular stream. In this context, timbre refers to the harmonic density or complexity of the tones used for each stream.

2. STREAM SEGREGATION

2.1 Factors of Stream Segregation

Stream segregation is a major branch of Auditory Scene Analysis and refers to the perceptual grouping of tones, resulting in the ‘streaming effect’ [11]. Since its inception, it has been considered vital in understanding the Cocktail Party Effect and key to replicating the human auditory systems ability to segregate blended sound streams. Preceding and contemporary research suggests that frequency distance, tone complexity, temporal distance, temporal coherence, and spatial location all play a critical role in stream segregation.

The role of frequency difference in stream segregation has been well-researched. Studies originating from early ASA research concluded that pure tones that were close in frequency were far more likely to group perceptually and form one ‘stream’ [12]. These findings have been supported by many other publications in the field to date and have been further expanded on [13]. The same con-

sensus is true for our understanding of temporal distance, where the rate of presentation (the interval between alternating sounds) has a direct influence on the threshold of which the segregating of streams occurs [14]. Where temporal distance generally refers to the alternating or sequential playback of tones, temporal coherence looks at temporally overlapping tones, and how the phase and synchronicity of various tones play a role in streaming. Despite a relative lack of publications addressing temporal coherence, arguments behind its importance in conjunction with (and even above) tonotopic models are well documented [15–17]. Spatial stream segregation (SSS) is another element of SS that has received less attention. Although it is clear spatial location is a key factor in segregating sound sources, there has been relatively little focus on spatial acuity. Researchers on the topic have suggested that spatial cues such as inter-aural level difference (ILD) and inter-aural time difference (ITD) play a crucial role in permitting high-acuity SS, particularly in the horizontal plane [18, 19].

The primary goal of ASA is to determine how, and when, these factors interact with each other to construct our perception of sound. What complicates this problem further is deciding what role attention plays in SS. Evidence to date suggests that while SS does occur involuntarily, there are also attention-dependent mechanisms within the human auditory system that are more perceptive [20]. More specifically, this increased ‘sensitivity’ appears to only occur after a certain amount of time, as evidenced in event-related potential (ERP) studies [21] corresponding to the generally accepted conclusion that ‘streaming’ takes time to build up [22]. Interestingly, attention is also suggested to have a developmental role in how humans segregate streams [23]. This, in turn, suggests that auditory processing mechanisms develop as we age, and that schema-based SS might play a larger role than the SS that occurs during ‘bottom-up’ processing.

While various conclusions and models mentioned in this section appear to have somewhat conflicting conclusions (tonotopy vs periodotopy and bottom-up vs top-down), it is clear that to some degree each play a role in building our perception of the sounds around us. The next section focuses on the different ways in which timbre is examined and utilized for the purpose of sonification.

3. TIMBRE IN SONIFICATION

3.1 Examples of Applications

The way in which timbre is utilized to represent data is generally unique to each sonification application, and in some cases, involve synthesis techniques such as amplitude modulation [24]. Another example whereby timbre was uniquely implemented is in the Monte-Carlo sampling of probability distributions, in which granular synthesis was employed to provide a felicitous auditory display of these data. This method for approximating probability densities accumulates large numbers of discrete samples that can be directly mapped to ‘grain’ samples taken from an audio waveform [25]. The resulting audio feedback inher-

ently varies in timbre, and when exaggerated with additional predictions of a users future state, alerts the user to correct their technique.

An example of timbre being used in parameter mapping sonification can also be found in an application that uses a form of differential sonification, which contrasts EEG data streams across varying conditions. Although its role in this example is somewhat minimal (the center frequencies providing most of the contrast), Hermann et al. propose adding more complexity to the timbre of the tones to enrich the sonification method further [26].

3.2 Analyzing Approaches

Despite a considerable amount of studies and publications about tonality in stream segregation, the implementation of timbre in sonification applications is rarely justified using such research. There has, however, been considerable discussion about musical timbre perception. Using multidimensional scaling (MDS), distance models have been used to organize sounds of differing timbres into a ‘timbre space’ [27]. In such models, dissimilarity ratings are applied to various sounds of differing timbre so that they may be placed accordingly into a timbre space. McAdams et al. also discuss the different perceptual weights individuals place on different dimensions, seemingly unrelated to musical training. Contrasting pitch and timbre, Krumhansl and Iverson found that in tone sequences timbre perception was weak and only apparent when pitch remained constant [28]. This tendency to focus on pitch variation over timbre variation is worth noting when designing a sonification application. It suggests that in an application where pitch is acting as the primary mapping, timbre might be used to relay additional information (e.g. variable relationships within a dataset) without distracting from the key data being relayed by pitch.

In relation to harmonic content, there has been a general consensus that the harmonic number of a complex tone corresponds to how well humans perceive pitch [29, 30]. However, the exact cause of this is less transparent. Researchers appear to agree that harmonic resolvability - the perceptual segregation of individual harmonics that occurs less between higher harmonics - is not the sole reason behind the poor frequency selectivity of complex tones with a high harmonic number [31, 32]. Researchers suggest that temporal envelopes are the alternative or concurrent cause behind this problem, which again raises the question to what extent is the auditory cortex tonotopically versus periodotopically persuaded [33].

Other interesting research looks at temporal limitations of recognizing timbral cues [34], and indicated that identifying sounds using timbre could occur at indeed very small duration samples (a few milliseconds for some). While this is theoretically good news for sonification through timbre in general, there is still the matter of a build-up time being required for stream segregation to occur. Overall, despite being somewhat niche, there is research occurring that looks at methods of using timbre specifically for sonification, although it is generally very specific.

These methods of dissecting timbre and utilizing it effi-

ciently in sonification vary from very simple to complex. There has been intriguing research into using models prevalent in speech recognition, to determine a ‘timbre space’: a suggested model for discerning the connection between the physical attributes of timbre versus our perception of it [35]. Terasawa et al. contrasted using Mel-frequency Cepstrum Coefficient (MFCC) vs Linear Frequency Coefficients (LFC) to model perception of timbre, and found the more complex MFCC model was the better tool for representing their orthogonal perceptual model. This presents us with an intelligent approach to modulating or even creating timbral cues compatible with our own auditory perception.

This paper looks specifically at auditory line charts, and seeks to examine how incrementing harmonics, following that of a sawtooth wave, affects the participants ability to isolate sonified trends from distractor trends. The study also tests participant ability to discriminate samples that differ by only one additional harmonic.

4. EXPERIMENT

4.1 Auditory Graphs

An auditory line chart or auditory graph is a sequential representation of quantitative data points mapped to pitch, and is a simple and effective way of presenting a dataset, typically one dimensional. These auditory graphs can be used on their own or to complement a visual display in a multimodal application. There have been interesting studies that test various encoding strategies given to participants to aid in the identifying and tracking of auditory graphs. Qualitative data have given researchers an idea of how participants instinctively approach identifying trends [36], which include the use of verbal labels; imagined visuospatial constructs; counting (mentally or foot tapping i.e. motor); and pitch memory. Further research sought to test these strategies in conjunction with distractor tasks that theoretically shared the same cognitive ‘workload’ (the visuospatial strategy was paired concurrently with a secondary spatial task) [37]. Results found these ‘distractor’ tasks were less disruptive than anticipated, but also showed that the visuospatial and verbal labelling strategies had no significant difference in performance.

The main focus of the experiment shown in this paper is to specifically look at how adjusting the harmonic content of certain streams might provide a means of temporarily isolating (or grouping) particular ‘trends’ of an auditory graph. While the overall aim is to show how auditory scene analysis is a valuable tool for sonification, an immediate practical benefit for auditory graphs would be the ability to provide an overview and/or contextual information using concurrent auditory streams when imparting associations between data columns that are relative to each other. One such example is a previous sonification application implemented by Pauletto et al. [24], where EMG (electromyography) channels were concurrently sonified.

4.2 The Study and Stimuli

The user study consisted of 43 participants between the ages of 20-40 years old, male and female. The participants came from various years of a Music and Technology programme, and as a result have a basic understanding of harmonics, and their role in timbre. It is worth noting that sonification is not something included in any learning module within the programme, and needed to be explained to all participants. The data used in this study is EMG data sourced from the UCI Machine Learning Repository [38], and was originally compiled in the University of Essex. More specifically, within the ‘Physical Action’ dataset participant 1 subfolder, the following samples were used: walking, standing, bowing, clapping, waving, and hand-shaking. Although not entirely relevant to this experiment, each dataset consists of 8 EMG channels of which the following 5 were used:

Channel 1	Right bicep
Channel 2	Right tricep
Channel 3	Left bicep
Channel 4	Left tricep
Channel 5	Right thigh

Table 1. EMG physical action dataset contents.

The first phase of the user study introduced the 43 participants to the concept of auditory graphs, and asked them to simply listen to a sonified example of a single line chart ‘trend’, and then link it to one of four visual trends. This test acted only to introduce the participants to auditory graphs and did not disqualify them from the rest of the study. The frequency range typically used in sonification is between 200-5000Hz [39], the range in which humans are the most sensitive. In this application, the range was set to 400-1400Hz which corresponds to the flattest range present in the contemporary equal-loudness-level contours [40]. This allows for the first number of harmonics present to extend into the more sensitive 2-5Khz range. After phase one, participants were presented with four A/B listening tests in random order, in which they were asked to listen to two samples and choose the one that most accurately represented the visually-presented trend. Participants were also given the option to choose ‘Neither’ or ‘Both’ in addition to ‘A’ or ‘B’, when answering the question: With which sample can you ‘hear’ the above trend best? Also included in each test was a question to determine how difficult the participant found choosing between A and B, answered using a 7-point Likert scale.

Each A/B sample contained five sonified trends i.e. the five channels of the EMG dataset mentioned in table 1. To maintain a consistent variability in each test, the first channel of the ‘walking’ sample was used in all four tests. However, to avoid participants then learning to listen for that trend, this first column was transformed so that it differed in each test, yet retained a consistent variability. This was achieved by mirroring these data for the second test, inverting it for the third, and mirroring and inverting it for

the fourth. The four remaining ‘distractor’ channels then differed for each test.

For each of these four tests, participants were presented with two samples: A and B, and were asked to choose the one that best represented the visual trend shown. The trend that was visually displayed for each test was the first column of each dataset. This trend acted as our target/focused trend (T). In Test 1, this first column in sample A was left unaltered in that it comprised only the fundamental (f). In sample B, however, the first harmonic (h1) was added to the fundamental, following that of a sawtooth wave (even and odd harmonics with an amplitude equal to the inverse of its harmonic number). The overall amplitude of each sonified channel was limited to ensure participants didn't simply identify the trend over another because of its loudness.

In Test 2, the first column/trend of the ‘walking’ dataset was mirrored and again visually displayed for the participants to match either sample A or B with (depending which best represented the visualized trend). This time, sample A ‘focused’ the trend using the fundamental and first harmonic, while sample B sonified the trend using the fundamental (f), the first harmonic (h1), and the second harmonic (h2). This continued on subsequently in each test as seen in table 2.

Test	Trend ‘T’	Sample A	Sample B
1	Original (O)	f	f+h1
2	Mirrored (M)	f+h1	f+h1+h2
3	Inverted (I)	f+h1+h2	f+h1+h2+h3
4	(M) and (I)	f+h1+h2+h3	f+h1+h2+h3+h4

Table 2. Breakdown of Tests 1-4.

By Test 4, the focused trend (T) in both sample A and B sounded far richer in texture than those in Test 1 and 2. It is also worth noting that the labelling of sample A and B were also randomized in each test to prevent participants basing their answers on those of the previous tests.

Two more tests - perhaps more tangential to the initial focus of the study - were included in the randomly ordered test pool, and contrasted slightly different A/B samples. Both tests again asked participants to choose the sample that best represented the visualized trend. In test 5, however, the focused trend (T) of sample A was sonified using the fundamental (f) and the first harmonic (h1), while sample B did so using the fundamental (f) and the fourth harmonic (f4). This was to gauge participant response to a starker change in harmonics. Test 6, again asked the same question using the same A/B format as above. In test 6, however, the focused trend (T) of sample A was sonified using the first 3 even harmonics, while sample B did so with the first 3 odd harmonics. This test was to determine if participants found that trends segregated more effectively when comprising either even or odd harmonics. While the research mentioned in section 3.2 suggests frequency selectivity tends to suffer in complex tones with a high number of harmonics, it is less clear as to how it fares with the addition of each lower harmonic in a sonification context.

5. RESULTS

The first phase of the study asked participants to link a sonified trend to one of four visual trends and resulted in 77 percent of the 43 participants getting it correct. While this part of the study was intended only to introduce the participants to the concept of auditory graphs, it helps put the rest of results into context. When asked which sample best represented the visualized focused trend (T) for each test, the participants answered the following:

Figure 1. Test 1 chosen samples.

Figure 2. Test 1 Likert response to choice difficulty.

In Test 1, participants found the trend that was sonified using the fundamental and first harmonic better than the trend that was sonified using just the fundamental, suggesting a slightly richer timbre is preferable when trying to isolate trends from other concurrently playing trends. In answer to the question of how difficult participants found choosing which sample best represented the visualized trend (T) in Test 1, most participants found the choice difficult.

Figure 3. Test 2 chosen samples.

Figure 4. Test 2 Likert response to choice difficulty.

In Test 2, participants still found the trend sonified with the more complex tone better at representing the focused trend (T), however there was over double the number of participants who found no significant difference between sample A and B, suggesting an arising lack in confidence in distinguishing harmonic variance. This is not, however, reflected as clearly by the answers on difficulty where less participants found the choice hard, although the difference is somewhat negligible.

Figure 7. Test 4 chosen samples.

Figure 5. Test 3 chosen samples.

Figure 8. Test 4 Likert response to choice difficulty.

In Test 4, where the harmonics present increased from three in sample A to four in sample B, participants were split in their choice in deciding which better represented the visualized trend. The majority found both samples adequately represented the trend equally. This suggests a clear lack of confidence among the collective participants in regard to distinguishing preference between a trend sonified with 3 harmonics vs 4 harmonics. Interestingly, the Likert responses suggests that participants were actually slightly more confident in their decision, relative to the other tests.

Figure 6. Test 3 Likert response to choice difficulty.

The results of Test 3 vary little from Test 2 as participants still find the sonified trend with the richer texture preferable in representing the visualized trend.

Figure 9. Test 5 chosen samples.

Figure 10. Test 5 Likert response to choice difficulty.

The results from Test 5 indicate a clear preference for trends sonified with a tone consisting of the fundamental and 4th harmonic over the tone with the fundamental and first harmonic. The majority of participants also found this choice the easiest to discern out of all the tests presented.

Figure 11. Test 6 chosen samples.

Figure 12. Test 6 Likert response to choice difficulty.

The final test examined how participants chose between a complex tone made up of the fundamental and the first three even harmonics versus a fundamental and three odd harmonics, for the purpose of representing the visual trend. Similar to Test 4, participants were split, with the slight majority deciding that both samples equally portrayed the visual trend.

After separating those who chose A and B and their Likert answers for each test, a Mann-Whitney U was performed to check for any significant difference between how difficult each side found making their decision ($P < 0.05$, two-tailed). As previously mentioned, the true sample identities

of A and B were randomized, however, in the context of understanding these results; A represents the sample with the least harmonic content, while B represents the sample with more harmonic content:

Test	A _{Mdn}	B _{Mdn}	U _{Val}	P _{Val}	A _n	B _n	S Diff
1	2.5	2.5	83	.406	8	26	No
2	2	2.5	80	.389	10	20	No
3	2	2	66	.395	8	21	No
4	2	3	62	.825	11	12	No

Table 3. Results of Mann-Whitney U Test for significance between choice difficulty for those that answered A versus B.

It is worth noting the accuracy of these results will be adversely affected by the imbalanced sample size for each, except where the result was split more evenly between A and B. The overall result suggests, however, that there was no significant difference in any of Tests 1-4. Those who chose A and those who chose B both found their decision equally difficult.

6. DISCUSSION

It appears that participants were most confident in Test 1 when choosing the sonified sample that they considered best represented the visual trend. This was expected as Test 1 had a more pronounced effect of contrasting the focused trend (T) using no added harmonic to segregate it from the others, versus the fundamental and first harmonic. This result confirms trends can be segregated from concurrently playing trends with reasonable efficiency by just adding the first harmonic with an amplitude equal to its inverse harmonic number i.e. half of the fundamental in this case. This is the case even when the overall trend amplitude is limited and remains equal to its distractor trend counterparts.

While incrementing harmonics still resulted in participants choosing the sample with the trend richest in texture for representing the visual trend, the results show a stark drop in choice confidence as the number of participants choosing 'Both' doubled after the addition of the second harmonic. By the addition of the fourth harmonic, participants were unable to collectively agree on a preferred sample. These results suggest that adding the first three harmonics to a sonified trends fundamental will significantly increase a users ability to segregate it from concurrently playing sonified trends without additional harmonics. However, adding a fourth harmonic results in diminished returns and does not improve on the benefit elicited by the use of three harmonics.

Skipping the first three harmonics and including just the fourth harmonic has also been proven superior over adding just the first harmonic in segregating a sonified trend. This could potentially allow for a more subtle approach to 'focusing' a sonified trend among other sonified trends, without overpowering the overall blend of sounds should that be preferable. Participant inability to agree on a majority

choice for Test 6 clearly indicates that even and odd harmonics act equally in their ability to segregate streams.

7. FURTHER WORK

Sonification is a prevalent tool used today across wide-ranging fields of research, and as such must be maintained and improved upon where possible. Research in human auditory perception, and Auditory Scene Analysis in particular, provide robust support frameworks for designing efficient and pragmatic sonification applications. Parameter-mapping sonification is just one branch of that tool, and timbre just one parameter within that. Furthermore, in this study, timbre was utilized only in terms of harmonic enrichment using additive synthesis. Other approaches might include mapping information to the audio descriptors outlined by McAdams et al. [27]. These include spectral centroid; spectral flux; and the logarithm of attack time (this might apply to scatterplots, for example). In future work, the authors of this paper aim to examine other parameters within this branch of sonification, using findings from ASA research to improve on sonification design strategies.

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